

A Mini-Review on Celiac Disease and Gluten-Free Diet's Influence on Gut Microbiota

Akash Patel MD

Department of Internal Medicine, Eisenhower Medical Centre, Rancho Mirage, California, USA

Citation: Akash Patel MD. A Mini-Review on Celiac Disease and Gluten-Free Diet's Influence on Gut Microbiota. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(17):1-6.

Received Date: 20 October, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 01 November, 2023; **Published Date:** 02 November, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Akash Patel MD, Department of Internal Medicine, Eisenhower Medical Centre, Rancho Mirage, California, USA

Copyright: © Akash Patel MD, Open Access 2023. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour* (ICMCRJ) (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Celiac Disease (CD) is an autoimmune disorder affecting the small intestine, primarily managed through a lifelong gluten-free diet (GFD). Despite the diet's role in symptom mitigation, a comprehensive restoration of gut microbiota remains elusive. This mini-review synthesizes current research on the influence of a GFD and gluten consumption on gut microbiota in CD patients. Studies indicate that CD patients exhibit a gut microbiota distinct from healthy individuals, marked by a reduction in beneficial bacteria and increased presence of potentially pathogenic species. While a GFD can partially restore microbiota balance, it often fails to achieve complete normalization. We also explore the potential role of probiotics as adjunctive therapy in CD management. Emerging evidence suggests that specific probiotic strains can improve microbiome imbalances, offering a targeted approach to treatment. Given the complex relationship between diet, microbiota, and autoimmune disorders, future research should focus on longitudinal studies and personalized medicine for a more holistic approach to managing CD.

Keywords: Celiac Disease; Gluten-Free Diet; Gut Microbiota; Probiotics; Dysbiosis

INTRODUCTION

Celiac Disease (CD) is a complex autoimmune disorder that primarily targets the small intestine and manifests in both intestinal and extra-intestinal symptoms.^[1] The condition predominantly affects individuals carrying specific genetic markers (HLA-DQ2, HLA-DQ8), although the mere presence of these genetic susceptibility markers alone is not sufficient to cause the disease.^[2] Gluten, a complex protein found primarily in wheat, barley, and rye, serves as a triggering environmental factor, especially in genetically predisposed individuals.^[1] The disease is characterized by a range of clinical symptoms, including diarrhea, abdominal pain, anaemia, and dermatitis herpetiformis.^[3]

The current standard of care for managing CD is a lifelong gluten-free diet. However, this treatment approach imposes a significant economic, social, and psychological burden on patients.^[4] This has led researchers to investigate additional factors that might contribute to disease pathogenesis and potential alternative or adjunctive

treatments. Among these, the gut microbiota has emerged as a crucial element that can modulate the immune response, influence gut barrier function, and possibly contribute to the onset and maintenance of autoimmune disorders like CD.^[5] Dysbiosis, or disruptions in the gut microbiota, has been increasingly recognized in a variety of disorders, including autoimmune diseases.^[6]

Studies suggest that gluten intake can directly affect the composition and function of the gut microbiota.^[7] Furthermore, the role of probiotics as a potential therapeutic intervention for restoring microbial balance offers an intriguing avenue for future research.^[5,7]

Given the burgeoning body of literature on the gut microbiome and its relationship with autoimmune and gastrointestinal disorders, this mini-review aims to synthesize current understandings on how a gluten-free diet impacts the gut microbiome in the context of Celiac Disease. We will delve into how gluten consumption and avoidance can affect the intestinal and oral flora and examine emerging trends in the application of probiotics for CD management.^[5,7]

This multidisciplinary approach aims to offer clinicians, researchers, and patients alike a comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationships between diet, microbiota, and autoimmune diseases such as CD, thereby potentially opening new avenues for future research and treatment modalities.

ROLE OF INTESTINAL MICROBIOTA IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF CELIAC DISEASE

The intestinal microbiota has a significant role in CD pathogenesis, specifically in gluten metabolism and modulation of immunogenicity. Strains such as Lactobacilli and Bifidobacterium spp. can alter the immunogenic potential of gluten peptides, and shifts in microbiota composition are known to impact intestinal barrier integrity.^[8-12] Notably, dysregulation of proteins like zonulin exacerbates epithelial permeability in CD patients, and emerging research indicates the possible role of microbial metabolites in epigenetic changes that influence autoimmune predisposition.^[11,13]

Recent cross-sectional studies have revealed altered fecal, salivary, and duodenal microbiota in CD patients, marked by a decrease in beneficial species and an increase in potentially pathogenic ones.^[14-17] Despite long-term adherence to a gluten-free diet, full microbiota restoration remains challenging.^[18] These observations underscore the complex interplay between the host and the microbiota, highlighting the need for continued research into microbial modulation as a potential adjunct therapy for CD.^[19,20]

GLUTEN-FREE DIET EFFECTS ON MICROBIOTA OF CELIAC DISEASE PATIENTS

The effects of a gluten-free diet (GFD) on the gut microbiota of CD patients remain an area of intense research, although conclusive evidence is sparse. Existing studies such as those by Golfetto et al.^[21] and Wacklin et al.^[19] point to a disrupted gut microbiota in CD patients compared to healthy controls, specifically with lower concentrations of beneficial bacteria like Bifidobacteria. Nistal et al.^[22] extended these findings, indicating that a GFD could partially restore the balance in gut microbiota but might not completely normalize it. Furthermore, the

persistence of symptoms in some GFD-treated CD patients has been linked to continued microbiota imbalance, particularly with the prevalence of Proteobacteria and reduced levels of Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes.^[19]

From a systematic review, it is suggested that GFD has the potential to bring the microbiota structure of CD patients closer to that of healthy individuals.^[23] However, this effect is not entirely straightforward and may vary depending on several factors such as the duration of the diet and the initial microbiota composition. It has been shown that commensal bacteria like Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus play a significant role in gut health, but their populations do not always return to normal levels even after long-term adherence to a GFD.^[24,25]

Although GFD appears to have a modulatory effect on the gut microbiota in CD patients, full restoration of a healthy microbiotic environment is still not guaranteed. Understanding these effects is crucial as gut microbiota plays a role in nutrient absorption, immune system regulation, and even symptom severity in CD. Future research could focus on how to complement GFD with other interventions like probiotics to fully restore gut microbiota balance.

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS OF GLUTEN-FREE DIET AND GUT MICROBIOME IN CELIAC DISEASE

While the necessity of a GFD for symptom relief and mucosal healing in celiac disease is unequivocal, the diet's broader impact on the gut microbiome has raised a number of clinical concerns. As detailed above, the GFD often fails to fully restore the gut microbiome to a healthy state, with deficiencies in beneficial bacterial species such as Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus remaining common issues.^[16,21,26]

The persistence of an altered gut microbiome, even after years on a GFD, suggests that a "one-size-fits-all" dietary approach may be insufficient for optimal patient care. This is particularly the case for CD patients with persistent symptoms, who display a distinct microbial pattern characterized by reduced diversity and elevated levels of Proteobacteria.^[19] In these instances, healthcare providers may consider microbiome analyses to personalize dietary or probiotic recommendations.

Given that GFD alone is insufficient to restore gut eubiosis, the adjunctive role of probiotics is receiving increasing attention. Studies indicate that the administration of specific strains, such as *B. longum* CECT 7347 or *B. breve* strains B632 and BR03, can ameliorate some of the microbiome imbalances and improve clinical outcomes in CD patients on a GFD.^[27,28] However, it's noteworthy that not all probiotic supplements have shown efficacy, underscoring the need for targeted, evidence-based interventions.^[29]

The GFD is often low in polysaccharides like fructans, which serve as prebiotics and support a healthy gut microbiome.^[30] Patients on a GFD may, therefore, benefit from nutritional counselling to identify alternative prebiotic sources and to avoid deficiencies in nutrients such as fiber, iron, and B vitamins, which can further exacerbate microbiota imbalances.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND CONCLUSION

Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to ascertain the long-term impact of a gluten-free diet on the microbiota in Celiac Disease (CD) patients. The exploration of specific probiotic strains and their therapeutic potential also merits investigation, as does the use of metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analyses for microbial function characterization. Personalized medicine approaches, including microbiota-based diagnostics, could offer new avenues for patient-specific treatment plans. Nutritional counselling may provide adjunctive support, given the frequent nutritional imbalances associated with a gluten-free diet.

In conclusion, while a gluten-free diet remains the cornerstone of CD treatment, it is insufficient for complete gut microbiota restoration. Multi-disciplinary strategies, including targeted probiotic therapies and personalized medicine, are necessary for a more holistic approach to CD management.

REFERENCES

1. Xingxing Wu, Lin Qian, Kexin Liu, Jing Wu, Zhaowei Shan. Gastrointestinal microbiome and gluten in celiac disease. *Ann Med*. 2021;53(1):1797-1805.
2. Bai JC, C Ciacci. World Gastroenterology Organisation Global Guidelines: Celiac Disease February 2017. *J Clin Gastroenterol*. 2017;51(9):755-68.
3. Lundin KE, LM Sollid. Advances in coeliac disease. *Curr Opin Gastroenterol*. 2014;30(2):154-62.
4. Allen B, C Orfila. The Availability and Nutritional Adequacy of Gluten-Free Bread and Pasta. *Nutrients*. 2018;10(10):1370.
5. María Carmen Cenit, Marta Olivares, Pilar Codoñer-Franch, Yolanda Sanz. Intestinal Microbiota and Celiac Disease: Cause, Consequence or Co-Evolution?. *Nutrients*. 2015;7(8):6900-23.
6. Fasano A. Leaky gut and autoimmune diseases. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol*. 2012;42(1):71-8.
7. Sanz Y. Microbiome and Gluten. *Ann Nutr Metab*. 2015;67 Suppl 2:28-41.
8. Alberto Caminero, Alexandra R Herrán, Esther Nistal, Jenifer Pérez-Andrés, Luis Vaquero, Santiago Vivas, et al. Diversity of the cultivable human gut microbiome involved in gluten metabolism: isolation of microorganisms with potential interest for coeliac disease. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol*. 2014;88(2):309-19.
9. Olivares M, M. Laparra, Y. Sanz. Influence of *Bifidobacterium longum* CECT 7347 and gliadin peptides on intestinal epithelial cell proteome. *J Agric Food Chem*. 2011.59(14):7666-71.
10. Martine Heyman, Juliette Abed, Corinne Lebreton, Nadine Cerf-Bensussan. Intestinal permeability in coeliac disease: insight into mechanisms and relevance to pathogenesis. *Gut*. 2012;61(9):1355-64.
11. Tamara Vorobjova, Helerin Raikkerus, Lumme Kadaja, Ija Talja, Oivi Uibo, Kaire Heilman, et al. Circulating Zonulin Correlates with Density of Enteroviruses and Tolerogenic Dendritic Cells in the Small Bowel Mucosa of Celiac Disease Patients. *Dig Dis Sci*. 2017;62(2):358-371.
12. Hooper LV, DR. Littman, AJ. Macpherson, Interactions between the microbiota and the immune system. *Science*. 2012;336(6086):1268-73.
13. G Serena, S Yan, S Camhi, S Patel, R S Lima, A Sapone, et al. Proinflammatory cytokine interferon- γ and microbiome-derived metabolites dictate epigenetic switch between forkhead box protein 3 isoforms in coeliac disease. *Clin Exp Immunol*. 2017;187(3):490-506.

14. Giada De Palma, Inmaculada Nadal, Marcela Medina, Ester Donat, Carmen Ribes-Koninckx, Miguel Calabuig, et al. Intestinal dysbiosis and reduced immunoglobulin-coated bacteria associated with coeliac disease in children. BMC Microbiol. 2010;10:63.
15. Maria Carmen Collado, Ester Donat, Carmen Ribes-Koninckx, Miguel Calabuig, Yolanda Sanz. Imbalances in faecal and duodenal Bifidobacterium species composition in active and non-active coeliac disease. BMC Microbiol, 2008;8:232.
16. M C Collado, E Donat, C Ribes-Koninckx, M Calabuig, Y Sanz. Specific duodenal and faecal bacterial groups associated with paediatric coeliac disease. J Clin Pathol. 2009;62(3):264-9.
17. Gangwei Ou, Maria Hedberg, Per Hörstedt, Vladimir Baranov, Göte Forsberg, Mirva Drobni, et al. Proximal small intestinal microbiota and identification of rod-shaped bacteria associated with childhood coeliac disease. Am J Gastroenterol. 2009;104(12):3058-67.
18. Raffaella Di Cagno, Maria De Angelis, Ilaria De Pasquale, Maurice Ndagijimana, Pamela Vernocchi, Patrizia Ricciuti, et al. Duodenal and faecal microbiota of celiac children: molecular, phenotype and metabolome characterization. BMC Microbiol. 2011;11:219.
19. Pirjo Wacklin, Pilvi Laurikka, Katri Lindfors, Pekka Collin, Teea Salmi, Marja-Leena Lähdeaho, et al. Altered duodenal microbiota composition in celiac disease patients suffering from persistent symptoms on a long-term gluten-free diet. Am J Gastroenterol. 2014;109(12):1933-41.
20. Maureen M Leonard, Stephanie Camhi, Tania B Huedo-Medina, Alessio Fasano. Celiac Disease Genomic, Environmental, Microbiome, and Metabolomic (CDGEMM) Study Design: Approach to the Future of Personalized Prevention of Celiac Disease. Nutrients. 2015;7(11):9325-36.
21. Lisléia Golfetto, Fernanda Duarte de Senna, Julia Hermes, Bruna Teles Soares Beserra, Franciane da Silva França, Flávia Martinello. Lower bifidobacteria counts in adult patients with coeliac disease on a gluten-free diet. Arquivos de gastroenterologia, 2014;51:139-143.
22. Esther Nistal, Alberto Caminero, Santiago Vivas, José M Ruiz de Morales, Luis E Sáenz de Miera, Leandro B Rodríguez-Aparicio, et al. Differences in faecal bacteria populations and faecal bacteria metabolism in healthy adults and coeliac disease patients. Biochimie. 2012;94(8):1724-9.
23. Iwona Kaliciak, Konstanty Drogowski, Aleksandra Garczyk, Stanisław Kopeć, Paulina Horwat, Paweł Bogdański, et al. Influence of Gluten-Free Diet on Gut Microbiota Composition in Patients with Coeliac Disease: A Systematic Review. Nutrients. 2022;14(10):2083.
24. Umberto Volta, Giacomo Caio, Francesco Tovoli, Roberto De Giorgio. Gut-liver axis: an immune link between coeliac disease and primary biliary cirrhosis. Expert Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2013;7(3):253-61.
25. Vriezinga SL, et al., Randomized feeding intervention in infants at high risk for coeliac disease. New England Journal of Medicine. 2014;371(14):1304-1315.
26. Raffaella Di Cagno, Maria De Angelis, Ilaria De Pasquale, Maurice Ndagijimana, Pamela Vernocchi, Patrizia Ricciuti, et al. Duodenal and faecal microbiota of coeliac children: molecular, phenotype and metabolome characterization. BMC microbiology, 2011;11(1):1-21.
27. Marta Olivares, Gemma Castillejo, Vicente Varea, Yolanda Sanz. Double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled intervention trial to evaluate the effects of Bifidobacterium longum CECT 7347 in children with newly diagnosed coeliac disease. Br J Nutr. 2014;112(1):30-40.

28. Andrea Quagliariello, Irene Aloisio, Nicole Bozzi Cionci, Donata Luiselli, Giuseppe D'Auria, Lúcia Martinez-Priego, et al. Effect of Bifidobacterium breve on the Intestinal Microbiota of Coeliac Children on a Gluten Free Diet: A Pilot Study. Nutrients. 2016;8(10):660.
29. Harnett J, SP Myers, M Rolfe. Probiotics and the Microbiome in Celiac Disease: A Randomised Controlled Trial. Evid Based Complement Alternat Med. 2016; 2016:9048574.
30. Jackson FW. Effects of a gluten-free diet on gut microbiota and immune function in healthy adult human subjects - comment by Jackson. Br J Nutr. 2010;104(5):773.